

The Prevalence of Piriformis Syndrome Among College Students

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Abstract— Background: Piriformis syndrome (PS) is a neuromuscular disorder caused by irritation of sciatic nerve by abnormal piriformis muscle. Piriformis syndrome is more common in women with a ratio of 3 to 1 and young people have more risk factors of getting affected with piriformis tightness that causes PS and later on lower back pain. Piriformis syndrome, a neuromuscular disorder, is also called wallet sciatica or fat wallet syndrome. It causes pain and numbness, tingling sensation in the buttock area and along the sciatic nerve pathway up to the leg.

Purpose: To find out the prevalence of piriformis syndrome among college students in Ariyur, Puducherry.

Study design: Prevalence study

Method: The convenient sampling method was used for the collection of samples based on selection criteria. Data from 100 samples were collected among 18-25 years of age group. The diagnostic tool used was the Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria. Further results were concluded through Statistical analysis.

Result: The Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria that were given to the participants, 18% were responded with high probable of piriformis syndrome.

Conclusion: Hence the study concluded the low probable prevalence of piriformis syndrome among the college students in Ariyur, Puducherry.

I. INTRODUCTION

Piriformis muscle originates from the anterior sacrum and sacroiliac joint, passes transversely through the greater sciatic foramen via the sciatic notch and inserts on the greater trochanter. The muscle is innervated by the ventral rami of S1 and S2 which join to form the nerve to the piriformis muscle receives its vascular supply predominantly from a branch of the inferior gluteal artery.^[1] When the hip is in extension, the piriformis muscle externally rotates the femur. The piriformis muscle functions as a weak hip when the hip is in flexion^[2].

Piriformis syndrome (PS) is a neuromuscular disorder caused by irritation of sciatic nerve by abnormal piriformis muscle. Women with a ratio of 3 to 1 are more prone to have piriformis syndrome, which is most likely caused by the broader quadriceps femoris muscle angle in the OS coxae. 6% of people who suffer from piriformis syndrome also experience low back discomfort. In a general population study, 2.2 – 19.5% indicated a yearly occurrence of PS, whereas 12.2 – 27% indicated a lifetime occurrence^[8]. Piriformis syndrome, neuromuscular disorder, is also called wallet sciatica or fat wallet syndrome. It causes pain and numbness, tingling sensation 1. in the region of the buttocks and up the sciatic nerve pathway to the leg.^[14]

Of the 196 female physical therapy students, Shazal nazir et al. found that 72 (36.9%) had a high score and a high likelihood of having piriformis syndrome. Merely four (2) 2.1% were Not considered to have piriformis syndrome in the majority of cases, 119 persons (61%).^[15]

Male students at the University of Lahore had a 5% frequency of piriformis syndrome, according to research by Soleman Warner et al. This illustrates the impact of extended sitting on students' radicular buttock soreness.

There are women diagnosed with a female-to-male a 6:1 ratio. Patients in their middle years are most frequently diagnosed with piriformis syndrome. The wider quadriceps femoris muscle angle in women's coxae can be used to explain this ratio.^[5]

F. Michel et al aimed to devise a clinical assessment score for PMS diagnosis and to develop a treatment strategy. Thirty healthy control volunteers and two hundred and fifty patients with disco-radicular conflict were enrolled. A variety of assessments were employed to generate a PMS diagnostic score.

A 12-point clinical scoring system was created, and a score of eight or higher was deemed "probable" for a PMS diagnosis.

The score has a 96.4% sensitivity and a 100% specificity, with a 100% positive predictive value and an 86.9% negative predictive value. 51.2% of patients responded well to combined medication and rehabilitation therapies. twenty-two patients (48.8%) in total. The suggested evaluation score might make PMS diagnosis and treatment more uniform.

About half of the instances involving injections of botulinum toxin involve rehabilitation. A comparison of 250 patients and 30.[10]

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

It was a prevalence study conducted on 100 subjects with piriformis syndrome, in the age group of 18-25 was taken from Sri Venkateshwaraa College of physiotherapy, convenient sampling method was used in this study and this study period was 6 months. Questionnaire used in this study was piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria. Female participants, Person who has seated for prolonged period, Person who has pain in buttock and leg subjects are included in this study. Leg length discrepancy, History of recent surgery and recent trauma, Male participants, Ages above 25 those were excluded in this study.

III. PROCEDURE

PIRIFORMIS SYNDROME DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

The identification of clinical signs suggestive of PMS and the standard methods used to examine the pyromanial muscle allowed us to create a clinical score for the diagnosis of PMS. This score consisted of 12 points each worth one-point (0 – 12) A diagnosis of PMS was considered to be ‘Probable’ if the score was greater or equal to 8, ‘Unlikely’ if the score was between 6 and 8, and ‘Not considered’ when the score was less than 6. The Sensitivity and Specificity of this score were calculated using this threshold value (for these calculations, the results less than 6 and those between 6 and 8 were combined). The Sensitivity and Specificity of the score were 96.4% and 100%, respectively. Patient has examined by using the special test (FAIR, Freiberg, HCLK). This scale’s questions focus on lower extremity. We can determine the piriformis syndrome by using this diagnostic criterion.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

- All the data were fed into the excel sheet for analysis. The scores obtained to Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria were added to get the result of piriformis syndrome among college students
- Then the data analysis was done for each student based upon the values of the questionnaire and scores that were evaluated for having buttock pain and leg pain
- Overall scores were obtained by using diagrammatic representation of data. The pie chart representation was used to determine the outcome variables of age, category and percentage of each individual

VALID AGE	FREQUENCY
18-20	47
21-23	35
24-25	18
TOTAL	100

Table 1: shows the age frequency of the college students who have been evaluated for the piriformis syndrome

Graph 1: shows the percentage of Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria

Table 2: Show the age category and percentage of Piriformis syndrome agnostic criteria

AGE	HIGHLY PROBABLE	LOW PROBABLE	NOT CONSIDERED
18-20	1	27	19
21-23	13	16	6
24-25	4	13	1

Graph 2: Show the age category and percentage of Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria

PIRIFORMIS SYNDROME DIAGONSTIC CRITERIA		
CATEGORY	NO OF INDIVIDUAL	PERCENTAGE
Highly probable	18	18%
Less probable	56	56%
Not considered	26	26%

Table 3: According to piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria, the fairly scored individuals are less probable are highly 56% and very few were highly probable 18%

Graphs.3 and 4 Show the percentage and scoring of the Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria.

V. RESULT

Out of the individuals who were given the diagnostic criteria for Piriformis syndrome, 18% indicated a high probability of having the syndrome.

The prevalence of piriformis syndrome using piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria were subcategorized as 18% of participants with high probable, 56% of participants with low probable, 26% of participants with not considered.

VI. DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to identify the prevalence of piriformis syndrome among college students in Sri Venkateshwaraa College of Physiotherapy in Ariyur by using piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria. In this study by conducting a survey revealed that piriformis syndrome among college students is low probable prevalent. Among 100 students were included according to the selection criteria. 56% of the students have a low chance of having piriformis syndrome. There is no evaluation of pain. Most of the individuals report buttock pain as a result of extended sitting.

In table 1; The valid age group and frequency were noted in that, the age group among 21-23 are highly probable.

In table 2; According to piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria, the fairly scored individuals are less probable are highly 56% and very few were highly probable 18%.

Graph 1 The percentage of Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria, 18% of highly probable, 56% of low probable, 18% of not considered.

Graph 2 shows the age category and percentage of piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria.

Graphs 3 and 4 Show the percentage and scoring of the Piriformis syndrome diagnostic criteria.

Shazal Nazir et al.,2022 In his study, 36% of students reported having low back pain in this study, compared to 6% of patients in the study who had PS. According to this study, 36% of pupils experience pain that can be triggered by stretches. In 80% of people, the sciatic nerve travels beneath the short piriformis muscle, which puts pressure on it. In his research found that 70.8% of students had sciatic nerve compression from prolonged sitting because of shortened piriformis muscles This study concludes that female physical therapy students of Gujranwala have a low to moderate probability of having piriformis syndrome, most of the participants that showed probability of piriformis syndrome involved buttock pain that triggered with prolonged sitting.

Farooq Islam et al (2022) In his study the prevalence of piriformis muscle syndrome among the subjects with low back pain data were collected using a non-probability convenience sampling method. The results are obtained from 219 participants. The overall Prevalence of PMS among in the people with low back pain was 18.3%. of the 219 patients, male and female Pace sign were respectively (85.8% negative and 14.2% positive). (81.7%) Negative and (18.3%) Positive Prevalence of piriformis muscle syndrome in the general population in age groups. In this research, they conclude that the positive prevalence rate is 18.3%. This indicates that many people with low back pain have PMS. The study that examined the prevalence of piriformis syndrome in the article above indicated that the condition was likely to cause buttock pain that was brought on by extended sitting and another article showed that piriformis muscle syndrome was present in a number of people who had low back pain.

In this study was concluded that low probability of piriformis syndrome and most of the participants showed involvement of buttock pain that triggered with prolonged sitting.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study concludes by stating a no significant prevalence of piriformis syndrome among the physiotherapy students in Sri Venkateshwara College of physiotherapy, most of the participants showed that low probability of piriformis syndrome involved buttock pain that triggered with prolonged sitting.

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